

Charge and Stability of Colloids. Part XXXI. Effect of Temperature and Non-electrolytes on the Variation of Conductance of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ Sols during Coagulation

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The specific conductance decreases with the dilution of each sol. During coagulation of each sol by K_2SO_4 , the increase in temperature causes the coefficient of specific conductance to increase with $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ sol and decrease with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol. In the absence of electrolyte, the specific conductance of each sol is found to increase on adding the non-electrolytes of high dielectric constant, but reverse is true with the non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant. At higher concentrations of each non-electrolyte, the decrease or increase in the non-electrolyte coefficient is small during coagulation.

According to Nordenson¹ and Wintgen and Hacker², the conductance in metallic sols is mostly due to impurities in dispersion medium. Dhar and co-workers³ observed that sols of ferric oxide, copper ferrocyanide, Congo red, As_2S_3 , silicic acid, etc. showed a marked influence in the conductance on ageing. On adding electrolytes in increasing concentrations to As_2S_3 sol⁴, it has been found that the conductance first increases rapidly, then more slowly, and finally the increase is linear. The rapid rise in conductance at the start of titration is due to removal of H^+ ion by the cations of the added electrolytes. The beginning of the linear portion of the conductance curve denotes the end of H^+ -ion removal process. Smoluchowski⁵ found that conductance of suspension was very much influenced by cataphoresis of the suspended particles. Conductance was found to be directly proportional to the number of particles in unit volume. Mukherjee⁶ observed irregular behaviour in variation of conductance with dilution.

Tareev and Baev⁷, on the basis of their mathematical equation, have shown that electrical conductance of a colloidal system is a function of concentration and particle size of dispersed phase and of temperature. Prakash⁸ has found that conductance of thorium arsenate and thorium phosphate gels is greater than the additive values of the conductances of their components. The temperature coefficients of thorium arsenate and thorium phosphate gels are lowered by 2% of their conductance at 35°. Mushran and Prakash⁹ found by extrapolation the temperature of zero conductance to be higher than -39° . The

1. *Kolloid Z.*, 1915, 16, 15.
2. *Ibid.*, 1932, 61, 335.
3. *Ibid.*, 1927, 42, 120.
4. Rabinovitch and Dorman, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 131, 313.
5. *Physikal. Z.*, 1905, 6, 529.
6. *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 63, 36.
7. *Colloid J., USSR.*, 1937, 3, 771.
8. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 907.
9. *Ibid.*, 1946, 50, 251.

temperature coefficient of conductance per degree of various sols was always less than 2% of the conductance at 35°. Chaturvedi and Bhattacharya¹⁰ consider that the enhanced conductance of the sol and electrolyte, as compared to the corresponding intermicellar liquid, lends strong support to the important role of ion-exchange phenomenon in the mechanism of coagulation.

Beg¹¹ found that the sol of copper ferrocyanide began to coagulate when increasing amounts of ethanol were added, leading to a decrease in the conductance. This decrease has been ascribed to the suppression of the released ions. An attempt has been made in the present communication to observe the effect of temperature and non-electrolytes on the coefficient of specific conductance during coagulation of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sols by K_2SO_4 .

EXPERIMENTAL

$\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sols were prepared in conductivity water and were purified by progressive dialysis. For determining conductances, 10 ml sol was placed in each of the 8 test tubes and 10 ml of electrolyte, water, and non-electrolyte mixture was placed in another set of 8 test tubes. All the 16 test tubes were placed in a water thermostat, adjusted at the desired temperature. Half an hour time was allowed to attain the temperature of the bath and then the contents of the test tubes containing the electrolyte were mixed with 10 ml sol, placed in another set of test tubes, at an interval of 15 minutes. For each set of coagulating systems, one-hour period was allowed after which 10 ml of the coagulating mixture was placed inside the conductivity cell and the conductance was measured. The process was repeated in presence of six concentrations of K_2SO_4 solution and also at three concentrations of each sol at different temperatures. Similar observations were also taken in presence of non-electrolytes at their different concentrations. From these observations, the temperature coefficient of specific conductance per degree and coefficient of sp. conductance per ml of the non-electrolyte for each sol have been calculated. All solutions were prepared in conductivity water, using A.R. grade chemicals and the dilution was also made with conductivity water.

TABLE I

Temperature coefficient of specific conductance/degree.

Conc. of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ sol = 8.54 g./litre. Sol taken = 10 ml. Total volume = 20 ml.

N/20- K_2SO_4 .	Sp. conduc. of sol at diff. temp. (mhos).			Temp. coeff. of sp. conduc./degree.	
	λ_{30} .	λ_{35} .	λ_{40} .	$\frac{\lambda_{35}-\lambda_{30}}{5\lambda_{30}}$.	$\frac{\lambda_{40}-\lambda_{30}}{10\lambda_{30}}$.
A. Pure sol + N/20- K_2SO_4 + water.					
0.0 ml	2.74×10^{-3}	2.96×10^{-3}	3.20×10^{-3}	0.0161	0.0168
1.0	3.01	3.26	3.52	0.0166	0.0170
2.0	3.19	3.47	3.81	0.0176	0.0194
3.0	3.37	3.58	4.00	0.0125	0.0187
3.5	3.48	3.75	4.12	0.0155	0.0184
4.0	3.55	3.85	4.22	0.0169	0.0189
4.5	3.62	3.93	4.32	0.0171	0.0194
5.0	3.70	3.99	4.41	0.0157	0.0192

10. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 132.

11. *Koll. Z. polymere*, 1957, 153, 164.

TABLE I (contd.)

$N/20$ - K_2SO_4	Sp. conduc. of sol at diff. temp. (mhos).			Temp. coeff. of sp. conduc./degree.	
	λ_{30}	λ_{35}	λ_{40}	$\frac{\lambda_{35}-\lambda_{30}}{5\lambda_{30}}$	$\frac{\lambda_{40}-\lambda_{30}}{10\lambda_{30}}$
B. 75% Sol + $N/20$ - K_2SO_4 + water.					
0.0	2.13×10^{-3}	2.31×10^{-3}	2.52×10^{-3}	0.0169	0.0183
1.0	2.38	2.57	2.83	0.0160	0.0189
2.0	2.56	2.78	3.05	0.0172	0.0192
3.0	2.74	2.94	3.22	0.0146	0.0175
3.5	2.82	3.02	3.32	0.0142	0.0177
4.0	2.89	3.10	3.41	0.0145	0.0180
4.5	3.00	3.22	3.50	0.0147	0.0167
5.0	3.07	3.34	3.64	0.0176	0.0186
C. 50% Sol + $N/20$ - K_2SO_4 + water.					
0.0	1.47×10^{-3}	1.62×10^{-3}	1.80×10^{-3}	0.0204	0.0225
1.0	1.70	1.85	2.02	0.0177	0.0188
2.0	1.98	2.05	2.25	0.0181	0.0197
3.0	2.03	2.22	2.44	0.0187	0.0202
3.5	2.17	2.34	2.59	0.0157	0.0194
4.0	2.30	2.47	2.74	0.0148	0.0191
4.5	2.45	2.64	2.93	0.0155	0.0196
5.0	2.57	2.82	3.07	0.0195	0.0195

TABLE II

Temperature coefficient of specific conductance/degree.

Conc. of $Fe(OH)_3$ sol = 7.512 g./litro. Sol taken = 10ml. Total volume = 20 ml.

$N/40$ - K_2SO_4	Conduc. of sol. at diff. temp. (mhos).			Temp. coeff. of sp. conduc./degree.	
	λ_{35}	λ_{40}	λ_{45}	$\frac{\lambda_{40}-\lambda_{35}}{5\lambda_{35}}$	$\frac{\lambda_{45}-\lambda_{35}}{10\lambda_{35}}$
A. Pure sol + K_2SO_4 + water.					
0.0 ml	2.07×10^{-3}	2.01×10^{-3}	3.07×10^{-3}	0.0180	0.0150
1.0	2.80	3.06	3.20	0.0186	0.0143
2.0	2.91	3.15	3.35	0.0165	0.0151
2.5	2.93	3.21	3.42	0.0191	0.0167
2.8	2.94	3.22	3.44	0.0191	0.0170
3.0	2.95	3.22	3.46	0.0183	0.0173
3.2	2.96	3.23	3.46	0.0182	0.0169
3.5	3.01	3.26	3.47	0.0166	0.0154
75% Sol + $N/40$ - K_2SO_4 + water.					
0.0	2.09×10^{-3}	2.28×10^{-3}	2.42×10^{-3}	0.0181	0.0158
1.0	2.18	2.39	2.56	0.0193	0.0174
2.0	2.26	2.45	2.63	0.0168	0.0163
2.5	2.29	2.49	2.66	0.0175	0.0162
2.8	2.33	2.51	2.66	0.0155	0.0142
3.0	2.36	2.54	2.74	0.0153	0.0161
3.2	2.38	2.56	2.78	0.0161	0.0168
3.5	2.43	2.60	2.82	0.0140	0.0161
50% Sol + $N/40$ - K_2SO_4 + water.					
0.0	1.46×10^{-3}	1.60×10^{-3}	1.74×10^{-3}	0.0205	0.0192
1.0	1.55	1.70	1.82	0.0194	0.0174
2.0	1.62	1.77	1.89	0.0185	0.0167
2.5	1.69	1.85	2.00	0.0189	2.0184
2.8	1.76	1.91	2.09	0.0171	0.0182
3.0	1.79	1.94	2.11	0.0168	0.0179
3.2	1.82	1.98	2.18	0.0176	0.0196
3.5	1.87	2.02	2.19	0.0181	0.0171

TABLE III

Non-electrolyte coeff. of sp. conduc./ml at 30°.
 Al(OH)_3 sol = 8.54 g./litre. Sol taken = 10 ml. Total volume = 20 ml.

<i>N/20-K₂SO₄</i> .	Sp. conduc. of sol. in presence of <i>n</i> -propanol (mhos).			Coeff. of sp. conduc. per ml of non-electrolyte.	
	1ml. λ_1 .	2ml. λ_2 .	3ml. λ_3 .	$\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{\lambda_1}$.	$\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_3}{2 \lambda_2}$.
Sol + <i>n</i> -propanol + <i>N/20-K₂SO₄</i> + water.					
0.0 ml	2.23×10^{-3}	2.01×10^{-3}	1.75×10^{-3}	0.0992	0.1081
1.0	2.55	2.22	1.93	0.1201	0.1223
2.0	2.83	2.40	2.11	0.1521	0.1272
3.0	2.94	2.57	2.25	0.1263	0.1172
3.5	3.04	2.65	2.32	0.1281	0.1163
4.0	3.12	2.73	2.41	0.1254	0.1161
4.5	3.20	2.70	2.47	0.1282	0.1141
5.0	3.29	2.80	2.53	0.1222	0.1162
Sol + formamide + <i>N/20-K₂SO₄</i> + water.					
0.0	2.84×10^{-3}	2.96×10^{-3}	3.13×10^{-3}	0.0423	0.0511
1.0	3.11	3.19	3.27	0.0257	0.0257
2.0	3.33	3.30	3.44	0.0180	0.0165
3.0	3.50	3.56	3.61	0.0171	0.0157
3.5	3.58	3.64	3.67	0.0168	0.0126
4.0	3.66	3.73	3.78	0.0191	0.0164
4.5	3.75	3.81	3.85	0.0160	0.0133
5.0	3.84	3.90	3.93	0.0156	0.0114
Sol + dioxane + <i>N/20-K₂SO₄</i> + water.					
0.0	2.42×10^{-3}	2.16×10^{-3}	1.85×10^{-3}	0.1080	0.1180
1.0	2.67	2.38	2.13	0.1080	0.1010
2.0	2.87	2.58	2.33	0.1010	0.0822
3.0	3.06	2.77	2.50	0.0946	0.0915
3.5	3.15	2.85	2.56	0.0952	0.0937
4.0	3.25	2.93	2.65	0.0985	0.0923
4.5	3.33	3.01	2.72	0.0961	0.0916
5.0	3.41	3.10	2.81	0.0909	0.0880
Sol + dimethylformamide + <i>N/20-K₂SO₄</i> + water.					
0.0	2.46×10^{-3}	2.23×10^{-3}	1.98×10^{-3}	0.0935	0.0975
1.0	2.67	2.43	2.19	0.0899	0.0899
2.0	2.90	2.61	2.37	0.1000	0.0914
3.0	3.08	2.76	2.50	0.1040	0.0941
3.5	3.15	2.84	2.65	0.0984	0.0794
4.0	3.22	2.93	2.73	0.0901	0.0761
4.5	3.28	2.99	2.70	0.0884	0.0741
5.0	3.39	3.05	2.86	0.1003	0.0782

TABLE IV

*Non-electrolyte coeff. of sp. conduc./ml at 30°.*Fe(OH)₃ sol = 7.512g./litre. Sol taken = 10 ml. Total volume = 20 ml.

N/40- K ₂ SO ₄	Sp. conduc. of sol. in presence of formamide (mhos).			Coeff. of sp. conduc./ml of non-electrolyte.	
	1 ml. λ ₁	2 ml. λ ₂	3 ml. λ ₃	$\frac{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1}{\lambda_1}$	$\frac{\lambda_3 - \lambda_1}{2\lambda_1}$
Sol + formamide + N/40-K ₂ SO ₄ + water.					
0.0 ml	2.40 × 10 ⁻³	2.48 × 10 ⁻³	2.56 × 10 ⁻³	0.0250	0.0333
1.0	2.60	2.67	2.65	0.0280	0.0300
2.0	2.63	2.68	2.78	0.0190	0.0285
2.5	2.67	2.75	2.86	0.0300	0.0356
2.8	2.69	2.76	2.89	0.0335	0.0372
3.0	2.72	2.83	2.94	0.0404	0.0404
3.2	2.73	2.86	2.95	0.0476	0.0403
3.5	2.78	2.92	3.02	0.0504	0.0432
Sol + dioxane + N/40-K ₂ SO ₄ + water.					
0.0	2.23 × 10 ⁻³	2.08 × 10 ⁻³	1.90 × 10 ⁻³	0.0672	0.0740
1.0	2.34	2.17	1.99	0.0727	0.0748
2.0	2.46	2.24	2.07	0.0894	0.0752
2.5	2.60	2.27	2.09	0.0920	0.0820
2.8	2.62	2.27	2.11	0.0992	0.0814
3.0	2.52	2.30	2.11	0.0873	0.0814
3.2	2.52	2.31	2.12	0.0870	0.0810
3.5	2.54	2.33	2.14	0.0827	0.0787
Sol + dimethylformamide + N/40-K ₂ SO ₄ + water.					
0.0	2.24 × 10 ⁻³	1.99 × 10 ⁻³	1.78 × 10 ⁻³	0.1120	0.1030
1.0	2.32	2.07	1.88	0.1080	0.0948
2.0	2.40	2.19	1.96	0.0875	0.0917
2.5	2.44	2.22	1.98	0.0902	0.0943
2.8	2.45	2.23	1.99	0.0898	0.0939
3.0	2.46	2.25	1.99	0.0772	0.0855
3.2	2.48	2.25	2.00	0.0928	0.0968
3.5	2.62	2.26	2.02	0.1030	0.0992

DISCUSSION

Temperature Effect

Decrease in sp. conductance has been observed when the concentration of each sol is decreased to 75% and 50%. This is, according to Smoluchowski³, due to the decrease in number of particles in unit volume. Temperature coefficient of sp. conductance per degree as compared to 30° for Al(OH)₃ sol and at 35° for Fe(OH)₃ sol has been calculated. This coefficient at all concentrations of K₂SO₄ increases with Al(OH)₃ sol as the temperature of the coagulating system increases. A different behaviour has been observed with Fe(OH)₃ sol. The temperature coefficient of pure sol decreases at all concentrations of K₂SO₄, but in presence of 75% and 50% sol, this decrease is observed only before the completion of coagulation and after it, an increase in this coefficient at higher temperatures is observed.

According to Smoluchowski¹², the conductance of a suspension may be very much influenced by the cataphoretic velocity of the suspended particles. The contribution of cataphoresis of particles towards conductance is given as:

$$\lambda_{\omega} = \frac{4\pi\eta v r (r + \delta) u^2}{N \delta} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where v is the number of particles per ml, u is the cataphoretic velocity under the gradient of one volt centimeter, N is the Avogadro number, η is the viscosity, δ is the thickness of double layer, r is the radius of the particles, and λ_{ω} is the conductance. During coagulation by electrolytes and also by raising the temperature, viscosity of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ sol is rapidly increased. The cataphoretic velocity, u , will also increase, but at the same time there will be a slight decrease in viscosity due to rise in temperature only and also a decrease in cataphoretic velocity due to high viscosity. The resultant of these factors will determine the conductance. Since the increase in coefficient of sp. conductance is observed even at early stages of coagulation on increasing the temperature, it may be assumed that at higher temperatures the viscosity and cataphoretic velocity are much more increased than decreased. After the completion of coagulation, there remains no suspension in the medium and hence there remains no question of its contribution towards conductance. After coagulation stage, the behaviour of the temperature coefficient of sp. conductance is like true electrolytes and therefore there is always an increase in the coefficient. This is true with each sol. The low values of this coefficient before coagulation with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol may be attributed to the small increase in sp. conductance, which is due to the lesser increase in viscosity during coagulation. Viscosity change with the increase in temperature of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sols is an important factor, which is responsible for the change in conductance.

Non-electrolyte Effect

It has long been accepted that the stability of colloidal system is strongly influenced by, among others, the electric charge on the disperse particles. Particularly in case of lyophobic sols, the coagulation rate is governed by the magnitude of electric repulsion and the van der Waals attraction. The force of attraction, according to Verwey and Overbeek¹³, remains constant, whereas the force of repulsion varies with the charge on particles. On the addition of non-electrolytes, the charge on particles can either increase or decrease, depending on the dielectric constant of the non-electrolyte added. The dielectric constant and mobility are related in the following equation:

$$\text{Mobility} = \frac{u}{E} = \frac{\xi D}{4\pi\eta} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where ' u ' is the velocity of the particles at the gradient of E volt, ξ is the zeta potential, D is the dielectric constant, and η is the viscosity. The parallelism between electrophoretic mobility and conductance has been shown by Ghosh and Henery¹³. The conductance of dispersion medium is related to the mobility of ions in equation (1). According to this equation, the conductance is directly related to the cataphoretic velocity. In Tables III and

12. "Theory of the Stability of Colloids", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1948.

13. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1963, 18, 157.

IV it is shown that in absence of electrolytes, there is a marked decrease in conductance with the addition of increasing non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant and *vice versa*. The increase in the value of sp. conductance coefficient per ml of non-electrolyte at its higher concentrations means that conductance is further decreased at higher concentrations of non-electrolytes, as compared to its lower concentration, whereas the decrease in the value of this ratio at higher concentrations means that conductance has suffered less decrease at higher concentration; just the reverse is true in presence of non-electrolytes of high dielectric constant. This decrease or increase in the value of this coefficient is either due to the increase or decrease in mobility of colloidal particles.

During coagulation in presence of K_2SO_4 and non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant, there is a decrease in the value of this coefficient; it is true of both the sols because lowering of dielectric constant decreases the mobility of ions, whereas the viscosity increases due to coagulation. On account of the predominant role of viscosity, the specific conductance at higher concentrations of non-electrolytes is less decreased and thus the value of the coefficient is less at higher concentrations. On the other hand, the increase in viscosity at higher concentrations of non-electrolytes of high dielectric constant is less and so the increase in this coefficient is less during coagulation with $Fe(OH)_3$ sol in presence of formamide the coagulation starting at higher electrolyte concentrations. The behaviour of dimethylformamide is abnormal and this is ascribed to some of its specific properties.

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